

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1900	Ernst Kris	1922	1922	1957		Austrian psychoanalyst and art historian	1900-1957
1900	Joachim Jeremias	1922	1922	1968		German Lutheran theologian, scholar of Near Eastern Studies and university professor for New Testament studies	1900-1979
1900	Veselin Beshevliev	1923	1925	1992		Bulgarian historian and philologist	1900-1992
1900	Shelomo Dov Goitein	1923	1923	1971		German Jewish ethnographer, historian and Arabist known for his research on Jewish life in the Islamic Middle Ages, and particularly on the Cairo Geniza	1900-1985
1900	Leslie White	1924	1927	1970		American anthropologist (advocacy of theories of cultural evolution, sociocultural evolution, and especially neoevolutionism)	1900-1975
1900	Wolfgang Schadewaldt	1924	1924	1968		German classical philologist (Greek philology) and a translator	1900-1974
1900	Gunnar Høst	1925	1925	1968		Norwegian philologist and literary historian	1900-1983
1900	Sukumar Sen	1926		1964		Indian (Bengali) linguist and literary historian of the Bengali literature, in Pāli, Prakrit and Sanskrit	1900-1992
1900	Wang Li (Liaoyi)	1926	1931	1986		Chinese linguist, educator, translator and poet, "the founder of Chinese Linguistics"	1900-1986
1900	Dorothy Burr Thompson	1926	1931	1966	w	American classical archaeologist and art historian at Bryn Mawr College and a leading authority on Hellenistic terracotta figurines	1900-2001
1900	Norman Tindale	1926		1968		Australian anthropologist, archaeologist, entomologist and ethnologist	1900-1993
1900	Marie-Louise Sjoestedt	1926	1926	1940	w	French linguist and literary scholar who specialized in Celtic studies, especially Irish mythology	1900-1940
1900	Joachim Begrich	1926	1926	1945		German biblical scholar and theologian	1900-1945
1900	Richard Rudolf Walzer	1927	1927	1969		German-British philologist and philosopher (Greek philosophy)	1900-1975
1900	Hjalmar Frisk	1927		1966		Swedish linguist in Indo-European studies	1900-1984
1900	Johannes du Plessis Scholtz	1927	1927	1965		South African philologist, art historian, and art collector	1900-1990
1900	Hortense Powdermaker	1928	1928	1968	w	American anthropologist (ethnographic studies of African Americans in rural America and of Hollywood)	1900-1970

1900	Daniel Sutherland Davidson	1928	1928	1952	American anthropologist who also did important work among the Australian Aborigines in the 1930s	1900-1952
1900	David Diringer	1929		1975	British linguist, palaeographer and writer	1900-1975
1900	Werner Krauss	1929	1929	1965	German university professor (Romance studies)	1900-1976
1900	Moses Hadas	1930	1930	1966	American teacher, a classical scholar, and a translator of numerous works	1900-1966
1900	Elinor Mullett Husselman	1932	1932	1965 w	American Coptic scholar and papyrologist	1900-1996
1900	Juan Bautista Rael	1933	1937	1972	American ethnographer, linguist, and folklorist	1900-1993
1900	Jean Nougayrol	1934		1960	French cuneiformist	1900-1975
1900	Alfredo Barrera Vásquez	1935		1980	Mexican (Native Maya) anthropologist, linguist, academic and Mayanist scholar	1900-1980
1900	Anneliese Bulling	1935	1947	1966 w	German-American art historian specializing in Chinese art and architecture	1900-2004
1900	Alexander Slawik	1936	1936	1971	Austrian sociological scientist, ethnologist, Nazi and professor in Vienna, who also worked on cultural themes	1900-1997
1900	Paulus Edward Pieris Deraniyagala	1939	No	1963	Sri Lankan paleontologist, zoologist, and artist	1900-1976
1900	André Dupont-Sommer	1949		1971	French semitologist	1900-1983
1901	Georges André Malraux	1920		1940	French novelist, art theorist, and Minister of Cultural Affairs	1901-1976
1901	Walther Rehm	1923	1923	1963	German literary scholar	1901-1963
1901	Walther Wüst	1923	1923	1945	German (Nazi) Indo-Europeanist and Vedicist	1901-1993
1901	Harry Hayden Clark	1924	1924	1971	American professor of English, specializing in American literature	1901-1971
1901	Henri Peyre	1925	1925	1980	French-American linguist, literary scholar and Sterling Professor of French Emeritus	1901-1988
1901	Raymond Firth	1925	1927	1968	New Zealander ethnologist	1901-2002
1901	Margaret Mead	1926	1929	1969 w	American cultural anthropologist, author and speaker in the mass media	1901-1978
1901	W. Cabell Greet	1926	1926	1966	American philologist	1901-1972
1901	Oliver La Farge	1926	No	1963	American writer and anthropologist	1901-1963
1901	Albert Wifstrand	1926	1926	1964	Swedish Altphilologe (Gräzist)	1901-1964
1901	Thomas Dale Stewart	1927	1927	1971	American founder of modern forensic anthropology	1901-1997

1901	Camilla Hildegarde Wedgwood	1927	No	1955	w	British anthropologist and academic administrator, the first British female anthropologist	1901-1955
1901	Elmar Muuk	1927		1941		Estonian linguist and author of a number of dictionaries and textbooks of the Estonian language	1901-1941
1901	Walter Havighurst	1927	1927	1969		American critic, novelist, and literary and social historian of the Midwest	1901-1994
1901	Kurt Erdmann	1927	1927	1964		German art historian who specialized in Sasanian and Islamic Art	1901-1964
1901	Mario Pei	1928	1937	1970		Italian-American linguist and writer	1901-1978
1901	George Herzog	1928	1937	1962		Hungarian-American anthropologist, folklorist, musicologist, and ethnomusicologist.	1901-1983
1901	Lucy Mair	1928	1932	1968	w	British anthropologist	1901-1986
1901	Jean Sauvaget	1929	1941	1950		French orientalist and historian, professor at the Collège de France	1901-1950
1901	Annemarie von Gabain	1930		1966	w	German scholar who dealt with Turkic studies, both as a linguist and as an art historian	1901-1993
1901	Gaston Waringhien	1930		1979		French linguist, lexicographer, and Esperantist	1901-1991
1901	Gordon S. Haight	1930		1968		American professor of English	1901-1985
1901	Ernest Cadman Colwell	1930	1930	1968		American biblical scholar, textual critic and palaeographer	1901-1974
1901	Edmund Taite Silk	1930	1930	1970		American Latinist	1901-1987
1901	Ralph Beals	1930	1930	1969		American anthropologist	1901-1985
1901	Renata von Scheliha	1931	1931	1954	w	German classical philologist and progressive aristocrat	1901-1967
1901	Charles Alexander Moore	1932	1932	1967		American philosopher, historian, sinologist, and writer	1901-1967
1901	Albert Béguin	1932	1937	1957		Swiss academic and translator	1901-1957
1901	Germain René Michel Bazin	1933		1966		French art historian, curator at the Louvre Museum	1901-1990
1901	Kalervo Oberg	1934	1940	1961		Canadian-American anthropologist and civil servant	1901-1973
1901	Anatole Lewitsky	1936		1941		Russian-French anthropologist	1901-1942
1901	George A. Kennedy	1937	1937	1960		American sinologist known for his studies of classical Chinese	1901-1960
1901	David Winton Thomas	1938		1968		British Regius Professor of Hebrew	1901-1970
1901	Gerhard von Rad	1938		1971		German Old Testament scholar, Lutheran theologian, academic, and University of Heidelberg professor	1901-1971

1901 Dorothy Way Eggan	1943 No		1965 w	American anthropologist noted for her research among the Hopi tribe	1901-1965
1901 A. M. Dale	1946 No		1963 w	British classicist and academic	1901-1967
1901 George Wynn Brereton Hun	1953		1967	British English linguist, anthropologist and historian	1901-1978
1902 Geneviève Thibault de Chambure	1920	1952	1973 w	French musicologist associated with the revival of interest in early music	1902-1975
1902 Émile Benveniste	1922	1927	1972	French structural linguist and semiotician	1902-1976
1902 Joseph Schacht	1923		1969	British-German professor of Arabic and Islam	1902-1969
1902 Arthur Capell	1924	1924	1962	Australian linguist	1902-1986
1902 Ephraim Avigdor Speiser	1924	1924	1965	Polish (Jewish) American Assyriologist	1902-1965
1902 Alfred H. Barr Jr.	1924	1946	1967	American art historian and the first director of the Museum of Modern Art in New York City	1902-1981
1902 Max Kommerell	1924	1924	1944	German literary historian, writer, and poet	1902-1944
1902 Lajos Ligeti	1925	1925	1972	Hungarian orientalist and philologist (Mongolian and Turkic languages)	1902-1987
1902 Harry L. Shapiro	1926	1926	1973	American anthropologist and eugenicist	1902-1990
1902 E. E. Evans-Pritchard	1927	1927	1970	British anthropologist (instrumental in the development of social anthropology)	1902-1973
1902 Julian Steward	1927	1929	1968	American anthropologist (developer "the concept and method" of cultural ecology, as well as a scientific theory of culture change)	1902-1972
1902 Günther Zuntz	1927	1927	1969	German-British classical philologist, professor of Hellenistic Greek and Bible scholar	1902-1992
1902 Georges Poulet	1927	1927	1969	Belgian-British literary critic	1902-1991
1902 Martin Noth	1927	1927	1967	German scholar of the Hebrew Bible who specialized in the pre-Exilic history of the Hebrews	1902-1968
1902 Li Fang-Kuei	1928	1930	1974	Chinese-American linguist (varieties of Chinese, reconstructions of Old Chinese and Proto-Tai)	1902-1987
1902 George Kingsley Zipf	1928	1930	1950	American linguist and philologist (statistical occurrences in different languages)	1902-1950
1902 Dumitru Popovici	1928	1935	1952	Romanian literary historian	1902-1952
1902 Charlotte Gower Chapman	1928	1928	1964 w	American ethnologist and an author	1902-1982
1902 Alfred Métraux	1928	1928	1963	Swiss and Argentine anthropologist, ethnologist and human rights leader	1902-1963

1902	Gustav Heinrich Ralph von Koenigswald	1928		1967	German-Dutch paleontologist and geologist who conducted research on hominins, including Homo erectus	1902-1982
1902	Daryll Forde	1928	1928	1973	British anthropologist and Africanist	1902-1973
1902	Felix M. Keesing	1928	1934	1961	New Zealand anthropologist who specialized in the study of the Philippine Islands and the South Pacific	1902-1961
1902	Milman Parry	1928	1928	1935	American scholar of epic poetry and the founder of the discipline of oral tradition	1902-1935
1902	Alexander Lesser	1928	1929	1965	American anthropologist of the Boasian tradition of American Cultural Anthropology	1902-1982
1902	Antanas Salys	1929	1929	1968	Lithuanian linguist, pioneer of experimental phonetics in Lithuania	1902-1972
1902	Henry Field	1929	1937	1969	American anthropologist and archaeologist	1902-1986
1902	Melville Jacobs	1929	1931	1971	American anthropologist known for his extensive fieldwork on cultures of the Pacific Northwest	1902-1971
1902	Michel Jonval	1929		1935	French linguist, specialist in Baltic studies, university graduate	1902-1935
1902	Henry R. Kahane	1930	1930	1971	American Romance philologist and linguist	1902-1992
1902	George Sherman Lane	1930	1931	1967	American linguist (Tocharian language)	1902-1981
1902	Gene Weltfish	1930	1950	1972 w	American anthropologist and historian	1902-1980
1902	Clyde S. Kilby	1931	1938	1981	American author and English professor, best known for his scholarship on the Inklings, especially J. R. R. Tolkien and C. S. Lewis	1902-1986
1902	Fritz Grossmann	1931	1932	1972	Austrian-British art historian	1902-1984
1902	Françoise Henry	1932	1932	1974 w	French scholar of early Irish art, archaeologist, and art historian	1902-1982
1902	Marion Frances Chevalier	1933	1933	1962 w	American philologist and photographer	1902-1990
1902	Ángel Rosenblat	1933		1984	Polish-Venezuelan philologist, essayist and hispanist of Polish descent	1902-1984
1902	G. I. Lieftinck	1933	1936	1972	Dutch academic specialising in medieval European manuscripts	1902-1994
1902	Margherita Guarducci	1935	No	1973 w	Italian archaeologist, classical scholar, and epigrapher	1902-1999
1902	Judith Tyberg	1940	1940	1973 w	American yogi ("Jyotipriya") and a renowned Sanskrit scholar and orientalist	1902-1980

1902	Allison Davis	1940	1942	1978	American Afro educator, anthropologist, writer, researcher, and scholar	1902-1983
1902	Burleigh B. Gardner	1941		1984	American social anthropologist, and Founding Chairman of Social Research Inc. of Chicago, Illinois, pioneering work in the field of consumer motivation research and quantitative marketing research	1902-1988
1902	Oscar Cullmann	1941		1972	French Lutheran theologian	1902-1999
1903	Maurice Delbouille	1923	1923	1973	Belgian linguist of French and Walloon	1903-1984
1903	Sebastián Cirac Estopañán	1925	1925	1970	Spanish philologist and linguist	1903-1970
1903	Siegfried Frederick Nadel	1925	1925	1956	Austrian-British anthropologist, specialising in African ethnology	1903-1956
1903	Hilde Zaloscer	1926	1926	1978 w	Austrian art historian, Egyptologist, Coptologist, essayist, novelist and a prominent expert of Coptic history and art	1903-1999
1903	Karl Marienus Deichgräber	1928	1928	1968	German classical philologist, was a member of the Nazi Party	1903-1984
1903	Edwin Denby	1928		1982	American writer of dance criticism, poetry, and a novel	1903-1983
1903	Jacques Heurgon	1928		1971	French normalian, Etruscan scholar and Latinist, professor of Latin language and literature	1903-1995
1903	Wilton M. Krogman	1928	1928	1983	American anthropologist	1903-1987
1903	Cora Du Bois	1929	1932	1969 w	American cultural anthropologist (culture and personality studies, psychological anthropology)	1903-1991
1903	Eric A. Havelock	1929	1929	1973	British classicist	1903-1988
1903	Jurgis Baltrušaitis	1929	1931	1963	Lithuanian art historian, art critic and a founder of comparative art research	1903-1988
1903	Ingemar Düring	1930	1930	1970	Swedish Classical Philologist	1903-1984
1903	Mark Hanna Watkins	1930	1932	1972	American Afro-American linguist and anthropologist	1903-1976
1903	Peter A. Boodberg	1930	1930	1972	Russian-American scholar, linguist, and sinologist	1903-1972
1903	Erminie Wheeler-Voegelin	1930	1939	1968 w	American anthropologist, folklorist, and ethnohistorian	1903-1988
1903	Louis Leakey	1930	1930	1968	British paleoanthropologist and archaeologist	1903-1972
1903	Erwin Reifler	1931	1931	1965	Austrian comparative philologist	1903-1965
1903	Sigmund Skard	1931	1931	1973	Norwegian poet, essayist and professor of literature	1903-1995
1903	Hans Vogt	1932	1936	1973	Norwegian linguist who specialized in the Caucasian languages, especially Georgian	1903-1986

1903	Anders Platou Wylle	1933	1933	1940	Norwegian philologist and humanist	1903-1940
1903	Mihailo Stevanović	1933		1973	Serbian linguist and philologist, professor at the University of Belgrade and a full member of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts	1903-1991
1903	Malcolm Guthrie	1934	1948	1970	British professor of Bantu languages	1903-1972
1903	William C. Hayes	1935	1935	1963	American Egyptologist	1903-1963
1903	Madeline Kneberg Lewis	1935	1937	1961 w	American archaeologist and professor of anthropology	1903-1996
1903	Sara Benet	1936	1944	1973 w	Polish anthropologist of the 20th century who studied Polish and Judaic customs and traditions	1903-1982
1903	Henri Lhote	1936	1945	1970	French explorer, ethnographer, and discoverer of prehistoric cave art	1903-1991
1903	Mary Butler Lewis	1936	1936	1961 w	American archaeologist, anthropologist, and public educator best known for her contributions to the fields of Mesoamerican archaeology and Northeastern and Central U.S. prehistory	1903-1970
1903	Roger Mynors	1937		1970	British classical scholar	1903-1989
1903	Lawrence Gwyn Van Loon	1938	No	1982	American general practitioner, amateur historical linguist and forger	1903-1985
1903	Germaine Dieterlen	1941	1951	1975 w	French anthropologist	1903-1999
1903	Israel Ruong	1943	1943	1973	Swedish-Sámi linguist, politician and professor of Sámi languages and culture	1903-1986
1903	Gerhard Scholz	1949	1958	1969	German university professor (Philology, German language and culture and Literary history)	1903-1989
1903	Ishida Eiichirō	1950		1968	Japanese scholar of folklore	1903-1968
1903	Hedwig Voegt	1952	1952	1963 w	German literary scholar	1903-1988
1903	Elizabeth Jacobs	1959	No	1975 w	American psychotherapist and anthropologist specializing in	1903-1983
1904	Robert Flacelière	1922		1980	French scholar of Classical Greek	1904-1982
1904	Francesco Gabrieli	1925		1979	Italian Arabist and orientalist	1904-1996
1904	Archibald Tucker	1926	1929	1971	South African linguist (African languages)	1904-1980
1904	Jean Mallon	1926	1926	1982	French palaeographer, specialist of Latin palaeography	1904-1982
1904	Friedrich Solmsen	1926	1928	1978	German philologist and professor of classical studies	1904-1989
1904	Robert Marichal	1927	1927	1985	French palaeographer and archivist	1904-1999
1904	Jovita González	1927	1930	1967 w	Mexican-American folklorist, educator, and writer	1904-1983
1904	Gregory Bateson	1928	1932	1980	British anthropologist, social scientist, linguist, visual anthropologist, semiotician, and cyberneticist	1904-1980

1904	Ján Stanislav	1928	1928	1977	Slovak linguist and specialist in Slavic studies	1904-1977
1904	Carleton S. Coon	1928	1928	1981	American physical anthropologist	1904-1981
1904	Friedrich Solmsen	1928	1928	1974	German philologist and professor of classical studies	1904-1989
1904	Heinz Kloss	1929	1929	1976	German linguist and internationally recognised authority on linguistic minorities	1904-1967
1904	Arthur P. Davis	1929	1942	1969	American African-American university teacher, literary scholar, and the author and editor	1904-1996
1904	Thorkild Jacobsen	1929	1929	1974	Danish historian specializing in Assyriology and Sumerian literature	1904-1993
1904	Albert Bruckner	1929	1929	1974	Swiss historian, palaeographer and medievalist	1904-1985
1904	Murray Barnson Emeneau	1930	1931	1971	American linguist (Dravidian languages, linguist areas)	1904-2005
1904	Gaston Vasseur	1930	1948	1971	French linguist	1904-1971
1904	Harry Hoijer	1930	1931	1970	American linguist and anthropologist (Athabaskan languages and culture)	1904-1976
1904	Giuliano Bonfante	1930		1978	Italian linguist and expert on the language of the Etruscans and other Italic peoples	1904-2005
1904	Liang Siyong	1930		1954	Chinese anthropologist and archaeologist	1904-1954
1904	B. F. Skinner	1931	1931	1974	American psychologist, behaviorist, author, inventor, and social philosopher	1904-1990
1904	Pei Wenzhong	1931	1935	1982	Chinese paleontologist, archaeologist and anthropologist	1904-1982
1904	Marie Margaret Keesing	1931		1961 w	New Zealand anthropologist and educator with strong ties to the Pacific	1904-1961
1904	Nils Holmer	1932	1938	1969	Swedish linguist, whose primary early focus of study was Celtic languages	1904-1994
1904	René Labat	1932	1938	1974	French Assyriologist	1904-1974
1904	Erwin Rosenthal	1932	1932	1971	German-British Hebrew scholar and orientalist	1904-1991
1904	A. Leo Oppenheim	1933	1933	1974	Austrian-American one of the most distinguished Assyriologists of his generation was editor-in-charge of the Chicago Assyrian Dictionary of the Oriental Institute	1904-1974
1904	Ian Hogbin	1934		1969	British-Australian anthropologist	1904-1989
1904	Jules Henry	1935	1935	1969	American anthropologist	1904-1969
1904	Manuel de Paiva Boléo	1935	1937	1974	Portuguese professor of Romance philology and Portuguese linguistics	1904-1992

1904	Léon Dostert	1936	No	1964	French-American scholar of languages and a pivotal proponent of machine translation	1904-1971
1904	Badiozzaman Forouzanfar	1936		1970	Iranian scholar of Persian literature, Iranian linguistics and culture, and an expert on Rumi (Molana Jalaaluddin Balkhi) and his works	1904-1970
1904	R. P. Winnington-Ingram	1936		1971	British classicist, an authority on Greek tragedy and ancient Greek music	1904-1993
1904	Joseph Campbell	1943	No	1972	American professor of literature at Sarah Lawrence College who worked in comparative mythology and comparative religion	1904-1987
1904	Charles Rostaing	1946	1947	1974	French linguist who specialised in toponymy	1904-1999
1904	Gwilliam Iwan Jones	1950	No	1971	South African Welsh photographer and anthropologist	1904-1995